

EFFECTS OF CARTOON MOVIES ON SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN OF SARGODHA DIVISION

Hamid Muhammad Ali Raza¹, Dr Uzma Qazi², Dr Abdul Basit³, Muhammad Kaqbad Alam⁴

¹M Phil Scholar, Department of Communication Studies, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan.

²Assistant Professor, Head of Media, Art & Design, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan.

³Assistant Professor, School of Media and Communication Studies, University of Management and Technology (UMT), Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

⁴Ph. D Research Scholar, (Journalism & Mass Communication) Department of Journalism & Mass Communication, University of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtoonkhwa, Pakistan

¹hamidmuhammadaliraza1@gmail.com, ²dr.uzmaqazi@greenwich.edu.pk, ³abdul-basit@umt.edu.pk, ⁴kaqbadalam@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15754779>

Keywords

Cartoon Movies, Electronic Media, Cable Network, Children, Academic Achievement, Language Change

Article History

Received on 20 May 2025

Accepted on 20 June 2025

Published on 27 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr Uzma Qazi

Abstract

Cartoon characters have significant influence on Sargodha's school-age children and effects of cartoon series on school-age children is critically investigated in this research study. For data collection, three hundred respondents (n=300) from Sargodha Division were carefully chosen using the convenience sampling approach. For data analysis, interpretation, and inference, statistical methods like correlation and chi-square are employed. Results indicates that children much prefer watching cartoons than engaging in outside social activities. However, they spend as much as two hours on their studies. Furthermore, it was observed that children like educational cartoons over stories about romance, humor, and horror. Additionally, it was observed that girls, people with elementary and high school educations, and children aged 9 to 12 were more likely than male viewers to watch cartoon programs. Despite the fact that female children watch cartoons more than male children, the findings indicate that children watch cartoon series quite often. Most children who watch cartoon shows on a regular basis get B marks in their prior school. The parents of the children also said that watching cartoon movies puts their children at higher risk for muscle and eye weakness than weight and sleep issues. Parents think that their children's attention, behavior, academic performance, health, and language are all more affected by viewing cartoon movies.

INTRODUCTION

Families, civilizations, and societal structures are all significantly altered by the use of electronic media. The lives of viewers of all ages are greatly affected by television (Havick, 2000). Most American households owns television, which has a significant effect on their life and, more significantly, on the development of the

children, who are exposed to it from nearly the time of birth. All age groups used to love television and cartoons, and people would stroll to the theater or watch cartoon movies at home for fun and pleasure since they are full of more humorous material that makes you laugh. However, this perspective has

changed, and many media genres are now seen as children's content. A child's brain development requires cartoons. According to research conducted in the 1990s, children's TV viewing habits increased by 70%, and Pakistani children are also affected by this exposure (Silverstone & Williams, 2004). While some have access to cable networks, the majority of children in Pakistan, watch cartoon channels that offer limited information compared to cable networks, which provide access to a wide variety of media content and foreign influences. Children's life has been dramatically transformed by cartoon films, which have also had an effects on their social lives. A significant portion of their daily lives now involves watching cartoon movies (Kubey & Csikszentmihalyi, 2013). Children like viewing their favorite comedies, adventures, and educational programs, but they also watch a lot of cartoons, fantasy, and fiction films. Animation's history dates back to 1300 B.C., and as time went on, it underwent several modifications. Since the first motion picture was displayed in public in 1800, cartoons have been a part of movie theaters. The praxinakisto scope was made in 1877 by Charles-Emile Raynaud in France, who also produced the first animation projection screen in 1892 (Meyrowitz, 1986). Stuart Black Ton's Humorous Phases of Michelsen, (2009) was the first animation film. Walt Disney established his business in 1923 and employed the first techno color process, which was recognized with an Academy Award in 1937. Early use of conventional techniques for drawing animation led to the development of CGI (Computer Generated Imagery), which took over the globe and transformed animation. Cartoons are multifaceted kind of entertainment that we provide to our children. Frequently, an image is more powerful than words. Cartoon movies may use this strategy to convey audiences any sort of tale.

Types of Cartoon Animation

While the rest of the world must import cartoons, the United States is the world's largest cartoon factory (Martell & Calderón, 2020). This type of entertainment is popular way for people in America and throughout the world to pass their free time. Benjamin Franklin started producing political cartoons in newspapers in the 18th century, and they

quickly became street-level phenomenon. Today, political comedy reaches its zenith in the age of television. Due to its high degree of social media integration, it has been quite popular in recent years. A political carton depicts the nation's current political landscape, as well as a particular political party, topic, and personality. There are political cartoons wherever you turn, including on TV, in newspapers, magazines, and on opinion and cartoon pages supporting the use of artistic visual art by social activists to convey political ideas, effect social change, and develop the brains of the next generation of people. In Pakistan, political comedy is also a common kind of entertainment that is expressed through a variety of mass media, including television, newspapers, magazines, the internet, and social media. The public's interest in political cartoons is demonstrated by the 35-minute political comedy section that is included on almost all high-rated news stations (Granier, 1990).

Cartoons are a very popular kind of entertainment that also serves as an educational tool by setting an example of proper behavior for children to follow. Children's cartoons are a common kind of cartoon. With its numerous well-known cartoon characters, like Tom & Jerry, Mickey Mouse, Suitemon, and Donald Duck, it is highly popular among children and teens. A popular animated film in the United States, Lion King has a good influence on American children and teenagers (Denney-Phelps, 2024). Cartoons serve as a moral compass for children's growth and a representation of society; as such, they reflect social events along with some surface-level substance. All cartoons are educational, and even violent material may teach children valuable lessons if they choose to learn them. The current study uses the following criteria to categorize the cartoon categories:

- Some children's cartoon films have educational elements; they may not include the entire topic or plot, but certain parts serve to teach children about social reality, language acquisition, and academic advancement.
- Cartoon comedy is a complicated process. During the print period, cartoons were only a type of humor. However, they have since evolved into a television genre that incorporates humor and

enjoyment. Children enjoy seeing these kinds of things and giggling at the funny parts.

- According to earlier studies, children, particularly boys, like watching action-packed cartoons. These violent or action-packed cartoons can lead to aggressive behavior by influencing children to mimic similar behaviors. The fundamental topic of non-violent cartoons is love, romance, affections, etc., and they usually do not contain any acts of verbal or nonverbal aggression.
- According to studies, girls are more likely than boys to watch these kinds of cartoons. Children are scared by cartoons that feature flimsy constructions. When they think about the world, they exhibit dread of things like darkness, walking alone, and similar stuff. Children who watch these kinds of cartoons also exhibit sleep issues and nightmares.

Effects of Cartoon Movies

Children's lives have been effected by cartoon films in a variety of ways, both positively and negatively (Habib & Soliman, 2015). On the one hand, they help children's mental development and improve their eyesight, but on the other hand, by confining them to a room in front of a television, they might have negative physical and psychological effects on the children. We may divide the effects of children watching cartoon movies into two categories based on their nature: good effects and negative effects. Watching cartoons may have a significant effect on children's eating and clothing habits, as well as how they like and dislike things, communicate, and behave (Bahri & Furqany, 2019). Cartoon Network is a full-time children's entertainment channel that solely shows cartoons. Sixty-eight percent of its viewers are between the ages of two and eleven. The first television cable that relied on cartoons to get viewers was Cartoon Network Channel. Through a satellite cable network, viewers of Cartoon Network may view their favorite shows in Pakistan. Since Pakistani children lack access to satellite cable networks, they primarily watch local broadcasting channels like PTV. In addition, Nick is a satellite cable network that started broadcasting in 1977 (Wilson, 2008). Its full name is Nickelodeon Pakistan, but most people call it ARY Nick. It has nearly all cartoon series

dubbed into Hindi, which is similar to Urdu, therefore Pakistani children choose to watch cartoon movies on Nick, which is quite popular among children. ARY Nick is the Nickelodeon cartoon channel in Pakistan, which is aired with the help of regional media. Turner Broadcasting launched Pogo, which debuted on January 1, 2004. Pogo Cartoon station, a television cartoon station that broadcasts in Tamil, Hindi, Telugu, and English, gave Chota Bheem a sneak glimpse of its success in Pakistan. Additionally, the majority of cartoon shows are either created in India, Pakistan's neighbor, or dubbed into Hindi. The most well-known Pogo shows include Mr. Bean, Chhota Bheem, Kumbh Karan specials, and Mighty Raju films. Since these cartoon channels are the most popular among children and are available to Sargodha children via local or satellite cable networks, they are included in the current study. Chota Bheem, Ben 10, Tom & Jerry, Ninja Hatori, Doremon, Oggi the Cockroaches, and Power Rangers are among the chosen animated series (Siddiqui, 2025).

Statement of the Problem

It would be a topic of considerable interest because it is widely assumed that children frequently practice watching cartoon movies with complete focus and interest (Khan et al., 2020). Children are the next generation's future, and since the advent of the picture box (television), they have become a common household item in every civilization that has contributed to global growth without being restricted by physical borders or sharing information. The majority of cartoon series and films that Pakistani children watch are imported from other nations, or they watch cartoons on foreign networks like Disney, Nick, and CN, among others. Distinguish between the effects of cartoon viewing habits on school-age children in urban and rural settings. Main research question is "what are the Effects of the cartoon movies on the school going children of the district Sargodha?"

Objectives of the Study

- To test the effects of cartoons on behavioral development of children of Sargodha division
- To determine the degree of attention paying on television and concentration on their favorites cartoon characters or movie.

- To determine the Effects of watching cartoon movies and excessive television on the school progress and achievements.

Literature Review

Watching Cartoon Movies Exposure

Electronic media has caused significant shift in the globe. Since 1990, television has dominated the media landscape, generating a wide range of programming tailored to different age groups and genders (Kackman et al., 2010). Meanwhile, children are exposed to a variety of genres, including dramas, fashion films, sports, news, and more. However, in the 21st century, where children are exposed to all of these media and more, cartoons are their favorite genre to watch. They spend more time and prioritize watching cartoons over other shows; they are familiar with the names, behaviors, and outfits of all the primary cartoon characters they often watch. Watching cartoons on television has significantly enhanced children's violent behavior, particularly among male children who prefer fighting to female children (Qouta et al., 2008). Additionally, the study discovered that although children of both sexes often fight both within and outside of their homes, boys fight with fellow boys a bit more frequently than girls. Because "Hindi" is more like "Urdu," Pakistani children can grasp it more readily. Instead than focusing on moving pictures, children appreciate cartoons more and comprehend the story's message better when they are presented in simple, intelligible English. Male and female children did not significantly differ in how much time they spent watching television cartoons (Giles & Heyman, 2005). Sargodha division children watched cartoons for two and a half hours every day, with Tom and Jerry being their favorite series. However, males like to watch violent action movies and television shows, and cartoon characters can have an effects on their buying habits. Another study looks into how cartoon movies affect children who are enrolled in school. They mimic the cartoon character's speech and behavior. Both short-term and long-term repercussions may result from their insistence on buying gowns, accessories, and other items based on their favorite cartoon characters. According to Pedük (2012), television plays an equally significant role in children's

life as it does in adults'. Watching television affects their mental, physical, and emotional health and leads to a purchase habit. Additionally, it has been shown that children between the ages of 10 and 11 are more engaged in language acquisition. Family members are also connected to one another by viewing cartoons together. Although it has some beneficial aspects, it also has a number of detrimental consequences on children's development, such as influencing local culture and national identification.

Television has a terrible effect on the physical and mental health of children and teens. Children are affected by television material in a variety of ways. It looked at the traits of parents' TV viewing habits and children's perceptions of the cartoons they seen. It was discovered that parents believed that the cartoon films their children had been watching for a long time had an effects on them. This shows how parents should feel about watching children's cartoons and that they believed that violent and aggressive scenes in cartoons might not physically harm their children. Davies (2001) pay particular attention to how children are affected by television and how media is ingrained in their minds to reward what they learn from it. With the help of TV, computers, videos, music, movies, and games, media are thoroughly woven into people's daily life. Children can get edutainment and infotainment from these media components, which can have some beneficial and natural consequences on their development. Children's primary source of amusement is cartoons. Children and teens spend their whole lives surrounded by electronic media, which has an effects on their neurodevelopment, nutrition, health, and academic achievement. However, the effects vary depending on the content and age of the kid. The original language and cultural values are undermined by foreign cultural effects through cartoons. Their eating habits are influenced by the deluge of advertisements for harmful foods. Research indicates a detrimental correlation between children's media exposure and academic performance. Adolescents who use their phones after bedtime suffer negative consequences. Parent education is essential for changing children's behavior and fostering their growth (Newman & Levine, 2012).

Harmful Effects of Watching Cartoon

Cartoons are the most popular among children and have been for decades, yet they often have a detrimental effect on children's unconscious minds. They either keep themselves occupied with productive work or spend more time watching cartoons. For children, watching cartoons has become more important than any other task. They enjoy watching cartoon films such as Oggy, Ben 10, Batman, and Tom & Jerry. It has been observed that cartoons frequently feature violent activities, such as explosions, gunshots, murders, beatings, and high-altitude jumps, which may negatively affect children's development and behavior. According to a study, over half of the population is ignorant of the significant influence that cartoons have on society since they are not aware of it (Rai et al 2016).

Effects on Mental Development

Using experimental study, Habib & Soliman (2015) examine the advantages and disadvantages of cartoon films for school-age children. According to them, the environment in which children grow up has a significant effect on their development and influences their beliefs. Because of the cartoon's colors and sound and visual effects, children are more drawn to it than to traditional academic study. In this regard, there are notable differences between viewing educational material and watching only amusement; individuals who watch educational shows are more involved in educational learning, reading books, and creating tales than those who do not. Respect for elders, helping the young, helping the poor, working in groups, solving problems, and being aware of the environment are some of the good consequences.

Social and Lingual Effects of Cartoon

Language was the medium used for mass communication (Mahsud et al., 2013). Language is a systematic system of signs, sounds, gestures, or symbols that people use to communicate thoughts and feelings to one another, as well as within their communities, countries, and the wider world. By communicating ideas and opinions from certain point of view, the media employ language as a tool to pique public attention. Over the years, linguists have been researching how language is used for communication.

Depending on the demands of the user, language is utilized to perform various communicative goals in various genres. Journalists, particularly cartoonists, employ language resources to draw in the public's attention and interest. They do this by using language elements persuasively and creatively to make an impression and enhance the material. Children's favorite pastime that provides them with entertainment is watching cartoons. The unrealistic events shown in cartoons are accepted by their naive thinking. They mimic what they see in cartoons, but they don't pay attention to everything that goes on around them. According to a study, children in Pakistan are being influenced by cartoons they watch at a quick pace because of multicultural cartoons. In contrast to Christian and Hindu religion and culture, Pakistani society is Muslim and has been negatively affected by Hindi and English cartoons. Psychologists have demonstrated that children's minds are highly developed in terms of learning, modeling, and imitating what they are exposed to. The beneficial and harmful effects of things cannot be distinguished by an innocent mind. Young brains behave similarly to wet clay. The moral, social, and religious values of children are being undermined by multicultural cartoons (Gökçearsan, 2010).

Theoretical Framework

A theory is a group of concepts. A theory is composed of results that are thought to follow the logical relationship the theory suggests. Theories help us understand the social phenomena we observe. To understand the concepts of mass media, one must become aware of how the world functions. Determining the influence of the media on people's attitudes, worldviews, and behaviors no matter how small is the primary objective of communication studies. After decades of study, Meadow (1980) claims that the only conclusion we can make on the effects of the media is that it varies. With an emphasis on Western and Japanese cartoons that are dubbed into Hindi and mimic the nation's official language, the primary objective of this study was to quantify the overall effects of foreign cartoon channels on the life patterns of school-age children in Pakistan. First, how children are exposed to cartoons, and second, how parents respond to their children's cartoon exposure,

are the two main issues of this study, which comes under the genre of tradition. The study necessitates a discussion of the theories based on information processing and observational learning. The study employs "Cultivation Theory," which is largely based on psychology and asserts that viewers pay attention to and learn from models that are viewed as attractive, powerful, fulfilling, and similar to themselves, in order to quantify the effects. There are a number of theories on the effect on their audiences, claiming both significant and limited effects (Gandhar et al., 2016).

Cultivation Theory

One of the most popular research techniques for examining the long-term effects of television consumption is cultivation analysis (Mohamed, 2011). Nearly every home in the Sargodha region has a television set, which tells the most of the stories through contents to its audience most of the time. Cultivation hypotheses are essentially created to measure the effects of violent and aggressive television content. Its use has been broadened to include potential perceptual effects of ingesting variety of media material as well as program-specific effects (Alam et al., 2024). The first effect of watching television, according to Gerbner, (1998) is that it gives viewers the impression that the world is more violent than it actually is. The second element affecting perception is the amount of time spent observing (Afzal et al., 2025). Excessive television watching has been linked to number of detrimental health effects. However, there is less attention paid to viewers' psychological well-being when it comes to their television-watching time. A viewer's viewpoint in real life will change if they often watch a particular conduct on television. Second-order cultivation effects are related to the consistent views, attitudes, and values that heavy viewers have about reality, while first-order cultivation effects likely include the acceptance of specific components of reality in reaction to TV portrayals of reality. Heavy viewers' perceptions of social reality have been effected by their exposure to television.

Methodology

The systematic process of addressing problems in the research is known as research methodology. To address the issue in the research study, researchers employ variety of techniques. Numerous metrics and research techniques are part of research methodology. In its most basic form, research methodology is the methodical process of gathering data, analyzing that data, and then further exploring the information that has been acquired. The study of tactics or procedures is known as methodology (Khan et al., 2024). This research study, which focuses on the effects of cartoon films on children's development and viewing habits, also uses techniques or approaches that have been applied in earlier studies.

Research design

The framework of a research project that outlines the specific kinds of data to be collected, along with the data source and methods, is called the research design. Quantitative methodology is employed in the survey in line with the criteria and nature of the argument, as the present study looks at how viewing cartoon movies affects school-age children. Data will be gathered, examined, and evaluated using the research methodology to determine how children in Pakistan's Sargodha area watch cartoons and the effects of cartoon films.

Survey Research

Survey research may be roughly divided into two categories: questionnaire surveys and interview surveys, depending on the data gathering technique. In terms of researcher time, effort, and expenditures, survey research is economical. Questionnaires are written forms that respondents fill out, whereas interviews are performed by the interviewer utilizing the interviewee's oral comments. Sir Francis Galton (2018) developed the survey questionnaire, a research instrument that consists of set of questions intended to consistently gather participant responses. There are two types of questions: closed-ended questions give responders a choice from a predefined list, while open-ended questions require them to answer in their own words.

Unit of Analysis

The children enrolled in the elementary, middle, and high schools in the Sargodha district make up the unit of analysis. School-age children from all regions of the Sargodha district make up the unit of analysis for the survey research. Its objective is to look at the broad psychological, physical, and societal effects of watching cartoons. Neumann et al., (2011) asserts that the term "population" is used to describe wide variety of circumstances from which a researcher draws a sample and is usually used in a speculative manner. According to Reynard, the population is the entire set of objects or events from which a sample is taken. First, the communication universe or population is identified. In this study, the universe selected for survey research comprises accessible or available respondents.

Sample and Sample Size

A sample is a portion of the population that acts as a representative model of the complete population, claim Wimmer and Dominik (2013). The sample is

described by Goode and Hatt (1952) as a smaller representation of a larger one. A sample is a small subset of the population used to represent the population. The parents of the respondents as well as school-age children from Sargodha and beyond make up the sample for this study. Due to time and financial constraints, this study examines the positive, negative, physical, and psychological effects of schoolchildren watching cartoon films. A total of 300 students make up the sample size, which is divided into two categories. School children (240 respondents) and parents (60 responses) regarding their children's cartoon movie viewing.

Findings of the Study

Cartoons are a big hit among children. Children get dependent on cartoons and like cartoon characters. Children spend more time watching cartoons than other forms of media. Cartoons have been shown to have range of effects in several research. Finding out the effects of cartoons is another goal of the present study.

Table 5.1 Frequency of Watching Cartoon Movies

Categories	Overall	Age			Education			Gender		Location	
		5-8 Years	9-12 Years	13-16 Years	Primary	Middle	High	Male	Female	Urban	Rural
Yes	95	95.7	97.6	93.2	96.3	92.4	96.3	93.3	96.7	92.4	97.5
No	5	4.3	2.4	6.8	3.7	7.6	3.7	6.7	3.3	7.6	2.5
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

No. of responses (n=300)

The frequency of seeing cartoon movies is indicated by the statistics in table 5.1. The study of the data revealed that, on average, a vast majority of children (95.0 %) watch cartoon movies, compared to (5.0 %) who do not. According to an age-wise study of the data, children between the ages of 9 and 12 (97.6%) watch more cartoons than those between the ages of 5 and 8 (95.7%) and 13-16 (93.2%). Education-wise data analysis, however, also reveals a little but not

statistically significant difference, with primary and high school students (96.3 %) preferring to watch cartoons over middle school students (92.4 %). Data analyzed by gender reveals that girls (96.3 %) prefer watching cartoons over boys (93.3 %). children in Sargodha's rural districts (97.5 %) prefer to watch more cartoons than children in the city (92.4 %), according to a location-wise study of the data.

Table 5.2 Frequency of Children Time Spending's

Categories	Overall	Education			Gender		Location	
		Primary	Middle	High	Male	Female	Urban	Rural
Less than 1 hour	51.7	62.9	36.3	56.3	62.5	48.3	55	55

1 to 2 hours	35	28	48.8	32.5	23.8	30.8	39.2	29.2
More than 2 hours	13.3	9.1	15	11.3	13.8	20.8	5.8	15.8
	100	100	100.1	100.1	100.1	99.9	100	100

No. of responses (n=300)

Above table reveals that in all, (51.7 %) of participants spent less than an hour on cartoon movies. The majority of primary school students (62.9 %) and boys (62.5 %) exhibit this brief use pattern. The largest percentage of any category, nearly half of middle school children (48.8 %), spend one to two hours. Additionally, they have the lowest percentage of customers that utilize the service for less than an hour (36.3 %), indicating that their schedules or levels of interest place them in the "medium" range. Long-term usage is more common in rural areas and among

women. The likelihood of spending more than two hours is twice as high for females as for males (20.8 vs. 13.8%). Compared to their urban counterparts, rural respondents are nearly three times as likely to go beyond two hours (15.8 % vs. 5.8 %). This can indicate distinct home patterns or a lack of other recreational opportunities in rural locations. The general trend is same for high school students. Their distribution follows the total rather closely (56.3 % < 1 hour, 32.5 % 1-2 hours, and 11.3 % > 2 hours), indicating that any treatments targeted at the "average" student will probably match the high school sector.

Table 5.3 Frequency of Watching Cartoon Channels Cartoon Network

Cartoon Network	Overall	Age			Gender		Location	
		5-8 Years	9-12 Years	13-16 Years	Male	Female	Urban	Rural
Very much	45.4	43.5	61.2	35.6	45	45.8	55.8	35
Much	22.9	39.1	17.6	23.5	14.2	31.7	12.5	33.3
Somewhat	23.3	13	14.1	31.1	30	16.7	26.7	20
Rarely	4.6	4.4	4.7	4.5	8.3	0.8	3.3	5.8
Not at all	3.8	-	2.4	5.3	2.5	5	1.7	5.8
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

No. of responses (n=300)

Above (Table 5.3) reveals the results of cartoon channel "Cartoon Network". The results of the current survey, which covers four channels accessible to the local population. as opposed to Cartoon Network (45.4%), Nick (30.0%), and PTV (21.7%) and POGO (49.6%). Children prefer to watch Cartoon Network very often (45.4%), much (22.9%), and somewhat (23.3%) rarely (4.6%) and not at all (3.8%). Children in the 9-12 age group (61.2%) like to watch Cartoon Network more than those in the 5-

8 age group (43.5%) and the 13-16 age group (35.6%), according to an age-wise examination of the data. The data's gender-wise analysis reveals no discernible difference, with female children preferring to watch cartoons on Cartoon Network more than male children (45.8% vs. 45.0%). According to the data analysis, children from Sargodha division (55.8%) greatly prefer to watch Cartoon Network, while children from outside the city (35.0%) do the same.

Table 5.4 Frequency of Watching Cartoon Channels Nick

Nick	Overall	Age			Gender		Location	
		5-8 Years	9-12 Years	13-16 Years	Male	Female	Urban	Rural
Very much	30	30.4	37.6	25	32.5	27.5	33.3	26.7

Much	24.6	26.1	20	27.3	14.2	35	23.3	25.8
Somewhat	23.8	17.4	22.4	25.8	23.3	24.2	25.8	21.7
Rarely	6.7	13	5.9	6.1	8.3	5	8.3	5
Not at all	15	13	14.1	15.9	21.7	8.3	9.2	20.8
Total	100							

No. of responses (n=300)

The results of an exclusive examination of the entire data on the cartoon channel "Nick" indicate that children prefer to watch the channel very much (30.0%), much (24.6%), and somewhat (23.8%) above the Rarely (6.7%) and not at all (15.0%) categories. The data's age-wise analysis reveals a little but not statistically significant difference: children in the 9-12 age group like to watch Nick more (37.6%) than children in the 6-9 age group (30.4%) and those in the 13-16 age group (25.0%). Data analyzed by gender

reveals little but not statistically significant difference, with male children preferring to watch Channel Nick more frequently (32.5%) than female children (27.5%). Compared to children from outside Sargodha city (35.0%), children from Sargodha city (55.8%) strongly prefer to watch Cartoon Network. According to data analysis, children from Sargodha division (33.3%) considerably prefer to watch cartoons on Nick, while children from other cities (26.7%) do the same.

Table 5.5 Frequency of Watching Cartoon Channels POGO

Pogo	Overall	Age			Gender		Location	
		5-8 Years	9-12 Years	13-16 Years	Male	Female	Urban	Rural
Very much	49.6	60.9	44.7	50.8	49.2	50	50	49.2
Much	27.1	17.4	40	20.5	20.8	33.3	27.5	26.7
Somewhat	10.8	8.7	7.1	13.6	14.2	7.5	11.7	10
Rarely	2.5	4.3	1.2	3	2.5	2.5	3.3	1.7
Not at all	10	8.7	7.1	12.1	13.3	6.7	7.5	12.5
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

No. of responses (n=300)

Above table 5.5 reveals the frequency of Pogo cartoon channel, with the former preferring to watch cartoon channel Pogo. , showed that, on average, children prefer to watch cartoons on the "Pogo" channel (49.4%), When it comes to watching the "Pogo" channel, children overwhelmingly choose the very lot (49.6%), much (27.1%), and somewhat (10.8%) categories over the rarely (2.5%) and not at all (10.0%) categories, Age-wise study reveals a little but not

statistically significant difference: children aged 5-8 years (60.9%) like to watch the Pogo Cartoon Channel. According to the exclusive research. more than those aged 13-16 years (50.8%) and 9-12 years (44.7%). However, the data's gender-wise analysis reveals a marginally significant difference between the percentage of female children (50.0%) who prefer to watch the Pogo Cartoon Channel and the percentage of male children (49.2%).

Table 5.6 Frequency of Watching Cartoon Channels PTV

PTV	Overall	Age			Gender		Location	
		5-8 Years	9-12 Years	13-16 Years	Male	Female	Urban	Rural
Very much	21.7	17.4	22.4	22	25	18.3	15	28.3
Much	12.5	17.4	15.3	9.8	7.5	17.5	17.5	7.5

Somewhat	14.2	13	18.8	11.4	18.3	10	16.7	11.7
Rarely	16.7	8.7	18.8	16.7	14.2	19.2	18.3	15
Not at all	35	43.5	24.7	40.2	35	35	32.5	37.5
Total	100							

No. of responses (n=300)

According to an examination of the whole data, children prefer watching cartoon movies on "PTV" very lot (21.7 %), much (12.5 %), and somewhat (14.2 %) over Rarely (16.7 %) and not at all (35.0 %). The data's age-wise analysis reveals a little but not statistically significant difference: children in the 9-12 age group like to watch cartoons on television more (22.4 %) than those in the 13-16 age group (22.0 %)

and those in the 5-8 age group (17.4 %). The data's gender-wise analysis reveals a little but not statistically significant difference, with male children preferring to watch cartoons on TV more than female children (18.3 %). According to data study, children from outside of Sargodha city (28.3 %) more prefer watching television over children from Sargodha city (15.0 %).

Figure 5.1 Children Favorite Cartoon Character (Heroism)

According to the data in (Figure 5.1), a significant majority of children prefer to watch all of the chosen cartoon characters, with Tom & Jerry being the most popular (54.2 %), followed by Doremone (51.7 %), Chota Bheem (50.4 %), Oggy & the Cockroaches (50.0 %), Ben Ten (40.8 %), Power Rangers (39.6 %),

and Ninja Hathori (33.3 %). According to the exclusive analysis, children who watch the character Power Rangers prefer to do so, but not significantly, as they fall into three categories: very much (39.6 %), much (15.8 %), and somewhat (15.0 %) as opposed to rarely (5.8 %) and not at all (23.8 %).

Table 5.7 children cartoon watching exposure and effects on their Time studying habits

Correlation Test		Time Study at Home in hours
Time Watch	Pearson Correlation	-.143 [*]
Cartoon In Hour	Sig. (2-tailed)	.027
	N	240

No. of responses (n=300)

A correlation test was used to examine the relationship between children's time spent watching cartoon movies and their time spent studying at home. The findings showed strong negative

association between children's time spent watching cartoon movies and their time spent studying and doing homework after school.

Figure 5.2 Children Learning from Cartoons

Children are seen learning from cartoon shows in the (figure 5.2). Overall, children learn a lot from the animation "Second Language Learning" (54.6 %) compared to learning how to love and share (42.5 %), solve problem skills (30.4 %), and be politically aware (7.1 %). In contrast to its Rarely (1.3 %) and never (12.1%) learning categories, the sole examination of learning from cartoons generally in terms of "second language" shows that children acquire language from cartoons very lot (54.6 %), much (22.1 %), and somewhat (10.0 %). Age-wise data analysis reveals a considerable difference, with children aged 13-16 learning a second language via cartoons at a rate of (59.8 %), compared to (49.4 %) for children aged 9-12 and (43.5 %) for children aged 5-8.

Summary and Discussion

The purpose of this study was to investigate how children's social interaction patterns, social morals, health, and development were affected by viewing cartoon movies. Research examines how the lifestyles of school-age children in the Sargodha division are affected by their exposure to cartoon networks, including Cartoon Network, Nick, Pogo, and PTV. The study's main ideas include children's television

cartoon watching habits, interest in and enjoyment of cartoon elements, health effects, parental limits and their reaction, purchasing behavior, and academic success. For data collection, three hundred respondents (60 parents and 240 children) were interviewed through questionnaire. Data analysis, interpretations, and graphical representations were done using statistical techniques such frequency tables, correlations, and the chi-square test. Overall, the study's empirical results about children's preference for cartoons over other television shows demonstrate this sentiment. Children in younger age groups (ages 5-8) and in lower class grades (primary) prefer to watch cartoons over their older counterparts. The data's gender-wise analysis confirms the findings of Odukamaiya's (2014) study from Nigeria, which found that children from urban regions watch more cartoon films than children from rural areas and that girls spend more time viewing cartoons than boys. The majority of the children's comments, according to the data analysis, fell into the very lot and much categories. Children like to watch cartoons on PTV less than they do on the other three cartoon channels (CN, Nick, Pogo) when it comes to viewing cartoon movies. Overall research results on cartoon channel

viewing revealed that, as compared to CN, Nick, and PTV, Sargodha schoolchildren prefer the cartoon television channel "Pogo." According to empirical research on children's favorite cartoon characters, "Tom & Jerry" is the most beloved figure among children, surpassing even Doremon, Chota Bheem, Oggi the Cockroaches, Ben-10, Power Rangers, and Ninja Hatori. Compared to other age groups, children in the 5-8 age range more like to watch Tom & Jerry. Analysis of the data by gender and educational attainment revealed minor differences, but not enough to be considered significant. The study's most crucial variable is time. To test the children's interaction patterns, statistical correlation tests were used to examine how much time they spent watching cartoon movies on television, how they spent their time studying at home after school, and how they spent their time engaging in social interactions outside of physical activities. The results indicated strong negative correlation between the two variables.

Less than an hour, one to two hours, and more than two hours were the three time categories that were used. The overall results of the study on children's time spent less than an hour revealed that children spent more time outdoors for one to two hours than they did watching cartoons or studying. The study of children's 1-2-hour time spent outside revealed a little but not statistically significant difference in the frequency of children engaging in outdoor social activities compared to viewing cartoon movies and studying. The significant number of children spending more than two hours demonstrated that, on average, children spend more time studying than they do watching cartoons or participating in outdoor social activities. They also spend less time engaging in these activities and more time studying. The majority of children choose to watch "educational" cartoon movie material above horror, comedy, love & romance, and fighting or aggression-based cartoons, according to the study of the data on children's interest in cartoon movie content. Data analyzed by gender revealed that whereas male children prefer to watch comedies, horror films, and violent cartoons, female children prefer to watch instructional cartoons.

According to statistics, children who like to watch horror films exhibit more severe terrified behavior, which can lead to long-term phobias like a fear of darkness or being alone.

One of the most crucial aspects of the study was determining how involved the children's behavior was after watching cartoons. The results showed that, on average, the children became much more involved in fighting after watching cartoons than those who did not watch horror. Numerous investigations by Goldmark, (2001), Gerbner et al. (1986), and others also found the same results. Ahmed & Wahab (2014) and Jose et al., (2014) According to age-wise study, children in urban primary schools between the ages of 5 and 8 are more likely than children in any other age, educational level, or geographic location to engage in fighting and exhibit violent behavior after viewing cartoon movies. However, compared to male children, female children were shown to be more stressed, anxious, and afraid after seeing cartoon movies, and they wanted to emulate what they saw. After viewing cartoon movies, children in the 9-12 age range were shown to be very interested in asking questions, which suggests that this age group is good and suitable for learning a model behavior. The vast majority of children comprehend Hindi and employ Hindi language terms in their daily interactions with friends and family, according to the overall empirical findings on "understanding Hindi language." By interviewing children about the meaning and everyday usage of Hindi language terms, language-based findings were noticed.

Summary and Discussion

Overall, this study meets all of its main goals. However, given its limitations, there were a number of tasks to complete, including how much cartoon movies affect children's physical and psychological development, how much they affect school-age children, how much they influence their language, social norms and values, and their health, and how much their parents are aware of the effects of mass media. The study's findings showed that children's behavior is greatly influenced by cartoon movies, that they are found to be more involved in the production of violence and aggressive behavior after watching violent acts in cartoon films, and that they exhibit

more fear after viewing horror content. The study's results also showed that Hindi is more common among Pakistani children since it is similar to Urdu, the country's original tongue. children can comprehend its fundamental syntax and phrases and frequently choose to utilize them in everyday situations.

The extent to which children learn from cartoons and if they replicate the actions they have learned from them were also being investigated. Age and education-wise studies illustrate the mental ways of children enjoying items to distinguish between male and female children's interests. According to the study's findings, parents are aware of the negative effects of excessive television viewing, particularly of cartoon films, but they choose not to regulate their children's viewing habits or establish a schedule for them. By doing so, they can reduce the negative effects of television. Parents also said that their children spend more time watching cartoons than engaging in any other activity, and that their physical health specifically, their eye-sight weakness is more at risk than other health-related factors. In order to promote positive moral, behavioral, and intellectual development, parents are advised to keep an eye on their children's interactions with television and learn about their viewing habits.

References

- Afzal, S., Nasir, N. U. A., Alam, M. K., & Khan, N. I. (2025). Effectiveness of Online Qur'an learning on Students' Performance of Qur'an Reciting. *ACADEMIA International Journal for Social Sciences*, 4(2), 1729-1743.
- Ahmed, S., & Wahab, J. A. (2014). Animation and socialization process: Gender role portrayal on cartoon network. *Asian Social Science*, 10(3), 44.
- Alam, M. K., Afzal, S., & Basit, A. (2024). Effectiveness of the Use of the Internet as Supplementary Tool for Academic Learning: A Case Study of University Students. *Journal of Social Sciences and Media Studies*, 8(1), 79-89.
- Bahri, K., & Furqany, S. (2019). The impact of cartoons on children's behavior. *Journal of Society Innovation and Development*, 1(1), 11-15.
- Davies, M. M. (2001). *'Dear BBC': Children, Television Storytelling and the Public Sphere*. Cambridge University Press.
- Denney-Phelps, N. (2024). *On the Animation Trail: 20 Years of Animation Festival History*. CRC Press.
- Galton, F. (2018). *English men of science: Their nature and nurture*. Routledge.
- Gandhar, S. S., Deshpande, J., & Borude, S. (2016). Effectiveness of cartoon movies as distracter on pain among children undergoing venipuncture. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 5(6), 2241-2242.
- Gerbner, G. (1998). Cultivation analysis: An overview. *Mass communication and society*, 1(3-4), 175-194.
- Gerbner, G., Gross, L., Morgan, M., & Signorielli, N. (1986). Living with television: The dynamics of the cultivation process. *Perspectives on media effects*, 1986, 17-40.
- Giles, J. W., & Heyman, G. D. (2005). Young children's beliefs about the relationship between gender and aggressive behavior. *Child development*, 76(1), 107-121.
- Gökçearslan, A. (2010). The effect of cartoon movies on children's gender development. *Procedia-social and behavioral sciences*, 2(2), 5202-5207.
- Goldmark, D. I. (2001). *Happy harmonies: Music and the Hollywood animated cartoon*. University of California, Los Angeles.
- Goode, W. J., & Hatt, P. K. (1952). *Methods in social research*.
- Granier, D. M. (1990). *The effects of the discussion of and the drawing of political cartoons as prewriting activities to increase fifth and sixth-graders' ability to write persuasively*. Louisiana State University and Agricultural & Mechanical College.
- Habib, K., & Soliman, T. (2015). Cartoons' effect in changing children mental response and behavior. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(09), 248.
- Habib, K., & Soliman, T. (2015). Cartoons' effect in changing children mental response and behavior. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(09), 248.

- Havick, J. (2000). The impact of the Internet on a television-based society. *Technology in society*, 22(2), 273-287.
- Jose, A., & Saraswathiamma, K. P. K. P. (2014). Effectiveness Of Cartoon Character's In Creating Brand Preferences Among Kids. *Journal of Economic Development, Management, IT, Finance, and Marketing*, 6(1), 61.
- Kackman, M., Binfield, M., Payne, M. T., Perlman, A., & Sebok, B. (Eds.). (2010). *Flow TV: Television in the age of media convergence*. Routledge.
- Khan, H., Ghafar, M. U., & Durrani, A. S. (2022). POPULAR CHILDREN'S TV PROGRAMS IN PAKISTAN. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 4(03), 386-396.
- Khan, N. I., Alam, M. K., & Afzal, S. (2024). Mosque, Mullah and Use of Social Media: Paradoxical Priorities of Peace and Religious Harmony in Pakistan. *Journal of Arts and Linguistics Studies*, 2(4), 2365-2388.
- Kubey, R., & Csikszentmihalyi, M. (2013). *Television and the quality of life: How viewing shapes everyday experience*. Routledge.
- Mahsud, M. N., Chaudhry, A. I., Amin, S., & Khan, M. S. (2013). Television channels' current affairs programs and students' gratification: A case of University of Sargodha. *Berkeley Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(1), 1-18.
- Martell, L., & Calderón, A. (2020). Public media. In *The Routledge Handbook to the Culture and Media of the Americas* (pp. 423-430). Routledge.
- Meadows, P. (1980). The Press and the communications media: a technological perspective. *International Journal of Comparative Sociology*, 21, 65.
- Meyrowitz, J. (1986). *No sense of place: The impact of electronic media on social behavior*. Oxford University Press.
- Michelsen, E. (2009). Animated cartoons, from the old to the new: evolution for the past 100 years. *Haskolinn Reykjavik*, 1-16.
- Mohamed, A. (2011). RESEARCH CODE OF ETHICS AMONG MEDIA SCHOLARS. In *INTED2011 Proceedings* (pp. 193-201). IATED.
- Neuman, W. L., Nardi, P. M., Berg, B. L., Jackson, W., Varberg, N., Robson, K., ... & Turner, L. A. (2011). *Research methods in communication*. Pearson (2011), London, UK. DOI.
- Newman, M. Z., & Levine, E. (2012). *Legitimizing television: Media convergence and cultural status*. Routledge.
- Odukomaiya, E. I. (2014). *Cartoons influence towards violence and aggression in school age children in Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, Eastern Mediterranean University (EMU)-Doğu Akdeniz Üniversitesi (DAÜ)).
- Pedük, S. B. (2012). A STUDY ON CHARACTERISTICS OF PARENTS' TV VIEWING AND CHILDREN'S OPINIONS ON THE CARTOONS THEY WATCHED. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(1).
- Qouta, S., Punamäki, R. L., Miller, T., & El-Sarraj, E. (2008). Does war beget child aggression? Military violence, gender, age and aggressive behavior in two Palestinian samples. *Aggressive Behavior: Official Journal of the International Society for Research on Aggression*, 34(3), 231-244.
- Rai, S., Waskel, B., Sakalle, S., Dixit, S., & Mahore, R. (2016). Effects of cartoon programs on behavioural, habitual and communicative changes in children. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 3(6), 1375-1378.
- Siddiqui, M. A. (2025). *Muslim Identity in Hindi Cinema: Poetics and Politics of Genre and Representation*. Taylor & Francis.
- Silverstone, R., & Williams, R. (2004). *Television: Technology and cultural form*. Routledge.
- Wilson, B. J. (2008). Media and children's aggression, fear, and altruism. *The future of children*, 87-118.
- Wimmer, R. D., & Dominick, J. R. (2013). *Mass media research*. Wadsworth Publishing Company.